

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

OLFML3 (olfactomedin like 3)

A Target Enabling Package (TEP)

Gene ID / UniProt ID / EC	56944 / Q9NRN5
Target Nominator	TREAT-AD, AMP-AD
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Therapeutic Area(s)	Alzheimer's disease
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CONTENTS OF TEP

Bioinformatic analysis: Target source & hypothesis

Protein constructs & expression methods: Baculovirus expression for structure determination

TARGET SOURCE & HYPOTHESIS

Why was the target selected? This target is found within a TMT proteomics network module that was highly correlated with cognition. This module (Module 42) contains several novel AD targets, including SMOC1 and SFRP1.

TRET-AD Target Risk Score: 3.33 (rank #2943, 88.2th percentile)

The TREAT-AD Center has developed a target ranking score encompassing genomics and genetics evidence. The Target Risk Score represents the gene target's general relevance to Alzheimer's Disease, and is the sum of

the target's Genetics Score and Genomics Score. Target Risk Score values range from 0 to 5, with 5 being evidence of the strongest association with AD. A complete description of the methodology used to calculate these scores is available [here](#). This score was taken from Agora, Data Version syn13363290-v62.

The TREAT-AD Target Risk Score for this target is 3.33 out of 5 (rank #2943, 88.2th percentile). The individual score components include 1.35 of 3 for genetics, and 1.98 out of 2 for genomics. The meta-analysis of proteomic and transcriptomic data sources used in the genomics score indicates that the expression of OLFML3, both protein and RNA, is significantly increased in brains from patients with AD.

The TREAT-AD Center has also developed a target categorization system specific to AD relevant processes, termed biological domains (biodomains). These biological domains are defined by constituent Gene Ontology (GO) terms and genes are then annotated to specific biological domains via GO term annotations. OLFML3 is not annotated to terms within any biological domain.

Cell-type specific expression is assessed using single-cell expression data from the Seattle Alzheimer's Disease Brain Cell Atlas (SEA-AD).

The distribution of expression values for all genes found in each broad cell type are displayed as violins. The expression of the target in subtypes within each broad class is shown as a point. Blue points show the summary expression of cells from individuals with no dementia, while red points show summary metrics of cells from dementia patients. Open circles reflect low confidence measures of expression. The expression of OLFML3 is not confidently detected in any cell type within this

dataset.

SUMMARY OF PROJECT

The OLFML3 gene is a fascinating new target for AD therapeutic development, as discussed in the next section, however little is known about its function in general biology or AD, so we are developing resources to facilitate future explorations. As parts of the OLFML3 target enablement package we are including purified protein, a characterization of the suitability of available antibodies for both biochemistry and histology, as well as a bioinformatic workup of the select target. We hope the availability of these resources will facilitate future investigations into OLFML3 and its biological role in AD pathogenesis.

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

The OLFML3 gene encodes an extracellular matrix like protein that is highly conserved across a broad spectrum of phylogeny. The 406 amino acid protein contains a variable coiled amino terminal region and the OLF like conserved domain at the carboxy-terminal portion of the protein(1)(UniProt: Q9NRN5). In higher mammals, the OLFML3 gene is expressed in the eye(1) and within microglial cells(2), and appears in the same cluster as homeostatic microglial genes like P2RY12(2). The microRNA mi-155 regulates this cluster of genes, down-regulating them in some higher vertebrate mammals(3). Targeting mi-155 rectifies microglial abnormalities within SOD1 mutant mice by restoring homeostatic microglial marker gene expression, phagocytic function and decreased the disease severity in the SOD1 mouse model of ALS(4), suggesting a role of OLFML3 in neurological disease and microglial functional regulation. OLFML3 is also expressed in pericytes and facilitates adhesion of forming vascular endothelium, with normal vascular integrity and PDGF mediated pericyte proliferation(5). The elimination of OLFML3 in mice results in partial embryonic lethality in roughly one-third of postnatal mice and comorbid leaky and malformed vasculature. The high incidence of vascular pathology in AD, as well as shifts from homeostatic to disease associated microglial states in AD, suggest that OLFML3 may have multiple roles in AD pathogenic progression. Consistently, ultra-deep proteomic studies of AD brains, CSF and serum identified multiple proteins associated with AD across sample types, including OLFML3(6), which was later found to be a component of AD amyloid plaques(7). This finding was expanded upon by later even larger scale brain proteomic studies in which OLFML3 was identified in module 42 (M42), a core proteomic AD-associated module that correlated strongly with both AD pathological progression and clinical dementia severity(7, 8). The role of OLFML3 in AD is unknown, but there are plausible links between vascular and innate immune dysfunction in AD that may be exacerbated by OLFML3 deficiencies(9), despite the observation that it is increased within M42. The mechanism of association with AD is not clear, however, the compelling links to multiple areas of AD biology warrant further exploration.

RESULTS – THE TEP

Proteins Purified

OLFML3_123-406_AviN_HisC: Baculovirus expression for structure determination. See **Additional Information** for experimental information on protein purification and methods.

CONCLUSION

The tools presented here provide a foundation for further biological investigation of the role of OLFML3 in AD.

FUNDING INFORMATION

The work performed by the Emory-Sage-SGC TREAT-AD Center has been funded by the National Institute on Aging through grant U54 AG065187.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Materials and Methods [insert protocols, example below]

Proteins Expression and Purification

All relevant plasmids are available on addgene: [TREAT-AD plasmid collection](#)

Gene name	OLFML3
Uniprot ID	Q9NRN5
Region	123-406

Description	Secreted scaffold protein that plays an essential role in dorsoventral patterning during early development. Stabilizes axial formation by restricting chordin (CHRD) activity on the dorsal side. Acts by facilitating the association between the tolloid proteases and their substrate chordin (CHRD), leading to enhance chordin (CHRD) degradation (By similarity). May have matrix-related function involved in placental and embryonic development, or play a similar role in other physiological processes
Synonyms	Olfactomedin-like protein 3
Construct ID	OLFML3_123-406_AviN_HisC_PBC039H04
Parental Vector	pFHMSP-AviN-LIC-C
Tag (N-terminal)	MKFLVNVALVFMVVYISYIYAAAGSAGLNDIFEAQKIEWHEGSAGGSG
Tag (C-terminal)	EFVEHHHHHHHH
Protein mass (with tag)	38908.09Da
Extinction Coefficient with tag (M⁻¹ cm⁻¹)	61560
Protein sequence (with tag)	MKFLVNVALVFMVVYISYIYAAAGSAGLNDIFEAQKIEWHEGSAGGSGGRRNEKYDMVTDC GYTISQVRSMKILKRFGGPAWLTKDPLGQTEKIYVLDGTQNDTAFVFPRLRDFTLAMAARKA SRVRVFPWVGTGQLVYGGFLYFARRPPGRPGGGEMENTLQLIKFHLANRTVVDSSVFP GLIPPYGLTADTYIDLAADDEGLWAVYATREDDRHLCALDPQLTDEQQWDTPCPRENAEA AFVICGTLVYVYNTRPASRARIQCSFDASGTLTPERAALPYFPRRYGAHASLRYNPRERQLYAW DDGYQIVYKLEMRKKEEVEFVEHHHHHHHH

Purified Protein	
SEC (step 1):IMAC, Ni sepharose	
OLFML3_123-406_AviN_HisC	

<p>IEC (step 2): SEC</p> <p>OLFML3_123-406_AviN_Hi sC</p>	<p>Hepes 7.4, 500 NaCl 5% glycerol n1—C4-11 4.5mg/ml; 4mg n2—C6-12 5.1mg/ml 3.3mg</p>
<p>Intact Mass Deconvolution:</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>Observed Mass:</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>Protein yield:</p>	<p>0.9 mg/L of culture</p>

<p>Expression and Purification Protocol</p>	
<p>Expression host</p>	<p>Insect cells: Sf9 (<i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i>)</p>
<p>Expression Medium</p>	<p>I-Max Insect Media W/ L-Glutamine, Wisent Biocentre</p>
<p>Transformation and storage</p>	<p>The baculovirus expression vector system (BEVS), specifically Bac-to-Bac Expression System (Invitrogen), employing <i>Autographa californica</i> multiple nucleopolyhedrovirus (AcMNPV) has been used for expression screening and production of target protein. The plasmid transfer vector containing the gene of interest was transformed into DH10Bac <i>E. coli</i> competent cells to generate recombinant viral bacmid DNA. Adherent Sf9 cells were then transfected with bacmid DNA to generate recombinant viruses used for the baculovirus-mediated production in the insect cells.</p>
<p>Expression</p>	<p>For the scale-up productions, suspension cultures of the baculovirus-infected insect cells, (SCBIIC) were prepared by infection of the Sf9 cells with the corresponding P2 viruses. On the day of production, 2 L of Sf9 cells (cell viability > 97%) in 2.5 L Tunair shake flasks or 4 L in 5 L reagent bottles were diluted to a cell density of 4×10^6 /mL. These cells were infected directly with 10-12 mL/L of suspension culture of baculovirus-infected insect cells and incubated at a lowered temperature of 25 °C, at 145 rpm. Infected cells' density and viability along with the cell sizes monitored after 72 hours post-infection time to be able to collect cells for purification at the optimal conditions when Sf9 cells are well infected, usually in 5-6 days after the post-infection time.</p>
<p>Purification buffers</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lysis buffer: 50 mM Tris (pH 8.0), 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP 2. Elution Buffer (EB): 50 mM Tris (pH 8.0), 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 250 mM imidazole 3. SEC buffer: 20 mM HEPES (pH 7.4), 300 mM NaCl, 2mM TCEP 4. TALON beads, equilibrated in Lysis buffer.
<p>Purification step 1: IMAC</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Spin down cells @6500RPM for 15min 2. Transfer each 1.5L supernatant to a 2.8L flask with 150ml 10X PBS. 3. Add (2ml/L) Ni-sepharose beads to the supernatant and shake at 100RPM at 18 °C for 60 min. 4. Transfer the supernatant + beads to an open column to collect the beads and keep the flowthrough.

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. Wash beads with 50CV of lysis buffer. 6. Elute protein with 5CV elution buffer. Analyze the EB fractions by SDS-PAGE and determine the protein yield using the Bradford assay. 7. Add beads (2ml /L) to the collected flowthrough for second binding same condition and repeat the same wash and elution after 1hour shaking.
Purification step 2: Size-exclusion chromatography (SEC)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Purify the protein further by Size-exclusion chromatography (SEC) on a HiLoad Superdex S200 26/60 column in SEC buffer at 3 ml/min. 2. Analyze fractions by SDS-PAGE. Pool fractions containing protein of desired purity for next step.

References

1. Rodriguez-Sanchez IP, Garza-Rodriguez ML, Mohamed-Noriega K, Voruganti VS, Tejero ME, Delgado-Enciso I, et al. Olfactomedin-like 3 (OLFML3) gene expression in baboon and human ocular tissues: cornea, lens, uvea, and retina. *J Med Primatol.* 2013;42(3):105-11.
2. Grassivaro F, Martino G, Farina C. The phenotypic convergence between microglia and peripheral macrophages during development and neuroinflammation paves the way for new therapeutic perspectives. *Neural Regen Res.* 2021;16(4):635-7.
3. Zhao S, Zhang J, Hou X, Zan L, Wang N, Tang Z, Li K. OLFML3 expression is decreased during prenatal muscle development and regulated by microRNA-155 in pigs. *Int J Biol Sci.* 2012;8(4):459-69.
4. Butovsky O, Jedrychowski MP, Cialic R, Krasemann S, Murugaiyan G, Fanek Z, et al. Targeting miR-155 restores abnormal microglia and attenuates disease in SOD1 mice. *Ann Neurol.* 2015;77(1):75-99.
5. Imhof BA, Ballet R, Hammel P, Jemelin S, Garrido-Urbani S, Ikeya M, et al. Olfactomedin-like 3 promotes PDGF-dependent pericyte proliferation and migration during embryonic blood vessel formation. *FASEB J.* 2020;34(11):15559-76.
6. Wang H, Dey KK, Chen PC, Li Y, Niu M, Cho JH, et al. Integrated analysis of ultra-deep proteomes in cortex, cerebrospinal fluid and serum reveals a mitochondrial signature in Alzheimer's disease. *Mol Neurodegener.* 2020;15(1):43.
7. Drummond E, Kavanagh T, Pires G, Marta-Ariza M, Kanshin E, Nayak S, et al. The amyloid plaque proteome in early onset Alzheimer's disease and Down syndrome. *Acta Neuropathol Commun.* 2022;10(1):53.
8. Johnson ECB, Carter EK, Dammer EB, Duong DM, Gerasimov ES, Liu Y, et al. Large-scale deep multi-layer analysis of Alzheimer's disease brain reveals strong proteomic disease-related changes not observed at the RNA level. *Nat Neurosci.* 2022;25(2):213-25.
9. Joseph LM, Toedebusch RG, Debebe E, Bastian AH, Lucchesi CA, Syed-Quadri S, et al. Microglia-Derived Olfactomedin-like 3 Is a Potent Angiogenic Factor in Primary Mouse Brain Endothelial Cells: A Novel Target for Glioblastoma. *Int J Mol Sci.* 2022;23(23).

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